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On the Late-variscan Occurrence of High-K Dykes at the Ossa-Morena Zone

Sobre a Ocorrência Tardi-varisca de Filões Ricos em K na Zona de Ossa-Morena

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Abstract

Geochemical data of the high-K felsic dykes of the Ossa-Morena Zone (OMZ) are here reported for the first time. These microporphyritic rocks were collected in the shoshonitic Veiros pluton and are interpreted as corresponding to the NW-SE dykes mapped in the area. Petrographic and geochemical studies of these K-rich rocks reveals vaugnerite affinities in the sense of Scarrow *et al.* (2009) and are here considered as the product of shoshonitic melts similar to those at the origin of Veiros massif, by a process of fractional crystallization. The presence of high-K magmatic rocks at the OMZ is interpreted as resulting from a multi-stage process involving a subduction-related metasomatic mantle source, most likely related with the closure of the Palaeozoic Rheic ocean.

Keywords: high-K magmas, felsic magmatism, vaugnerites, Ossa-Morena Zone, Late Variscan dykes.

Resumo

Dados geoquímicos relativos a filões félsicos potássicos da Zona Ossa-Morena (ZOM) são aqui apresentados pela primeira vez. Estas rochas microporfíricas foram recolhidas no maciço de Veiros e são interpretadas como correspondentes aos filões de direcção NW-SE cartografados na área. Estudos petrográficos e geoquímicos destas rochas ricas em potássio apontam para afinidades vaugneríticas na acepção de Scarrow *et al.* (2009). Os magmas de composição vaugnerítica são considerados produtos de cristalização fracionada de magmas shoshoníticos similares aos que deram origem ao Maciço de Veiros. A presença de rochas magmáticas ricas em potássio na ZOM é interpretada como o resultado de um processo multifásico envolvendo fonte(s) mantélica(s) metassomatizada(s) durante a subducção do oceano Paleozóico Rheic sob a ZOM.

Palavras-chave: magmas ricos em K, magmatismo félsico, vaugneritos, Zona de Ossa-Morena, filões tardi-Variscos.

Introduction

Late Variscan dykes at the Portuguese side of the Ossa-Morena Zone (OMZ) have been poorly studied, with a few exceptions (e.g. Lains, 2017; Henriques *et al.*, 2016; Santos *et al.*, 1990; Mata and Munhá, 1986).

In the region of the Veiros and Vale de Maceira, microdiorites and microtonalites NW-SE trending dykes were mapped near and across the shoshonitic plutons (e.g. Costa *et al.*, 1990) close to the contact of Estremoz-Barrancos and Alter do Chão-Elvas sectors (Gonçalves *et al.*, 1975). Three samples of those microporphyritic rocks were collected inside the Veiros pluton which allow to evidence, for the first time at the OMZ, the presence of high-K dykes with vaugnerite affinities (see also Lains, 2017).

Petrography and mineral chemistry

The studied dykes are mesocratic microporphyritic rocks with whitish grey phenocrysts, easy recognised in hand specimen.

The groundmass is very fine grained and composed of quartz, oligoclasic to albitic plagioclase and biotite (or minerals resulting of its hydrothermal alteration, such as chlorite and actinolite), rare calcite and zeolites (Fig. 1).

The phenocrysts are mostly sub-euhedral plagioclase (up to 2 mm) with andesinic cores and oligoclasic rims and, more rarely, of quartz and / or alkali feldspar.

Biotites (s.s.) are characterized by low-Ti (~1.5 wt.% TiO₂) and high-K (~10 wt.% K₂O) contents and are classified as aluminopotassic biotites (Nachit *et al.*, 1985).

The mineralogical composition of these rocks fit well the definition of vaugnerites: “dyke rock consisting of major amounts of biotite, hornblende and plagioclase and a little orthoclase.” (glossary in Le Maitre, 2002).

Geochemistry

The whole-rock analyses are very similar for all the studied samples. They are acid (SiO₂: from 64.95 to 66.23 wt. %) and sub-alkaline, plotting close to the transition between sub-alkaline and alkaline rocks on the TAS diagram. Their K-rich characteristics are well evident on the K₂O-SiO₂ diagram where they plot on the field of high-K rocks (i.e. HKCA). Other characteristics are low TiO₂ (0.59-0.62 wt. %), high LILE (e.g. Ba: 820-1186 ppm); high K₂O/Na₂O (0.92-1.00); high LILE/HFSE (e.g. Ba/Nb: 81.19-119.80); high Th/Yb (19.44-21.26); moderated high Th/U (4.34-4.74); high LREE/HREE (e.g. La/Yb: 38.80-41.75) and low Nb/Ta (12.33-13.20).

These rocks are metaluminous to slightly peraluminous, magnesian and calc-alkalic according to Frost *et al.* (2001) classification for granitic rocks (s.l.).

Fig. 1 – Microphotography of a vaugnerite dyke at the OMZ. Note the optical zoning of plagioclase phenocrysts.

Vaugnerite affinity? Comparative geochemistry

An attempt to discriminate rock associations that plot in the shoshonite and HKCA fields in the K₂O-SiO₂ diagram has been made by Scarrow *et al.* (2009). These authors discriminated three rock-associations 1) shoshonite; 2) vaugnerite; and 3) potassic lamprophyre. These authors, and references there in, extended the concepts like vaugnerite and shoshonites to rock associations with

composition up to acid characteristics (i.e. $\text{SiO}_2 > 63 \text{ wt.}\%$).

The sampled rocks are characterized by La/Yb ratios ~ 38 clearly higher than the typical values reported for shoshonites ($\bar{x} = 21$), lower than those of K-lamprophyres ($\bar{x} = 49$), but similar to those of the vaugnerites ($\bar{x} = 34$) described by Scarrow *et al.* (2009). Moreover they are distinguishable from both K-lamprophyres and shoshonites by Nb/Ta ~ 12 -13, which is significantly lower than the chondritic value (~ 17 ; Sun and McDonough, 1989), characterizing both shoshonites and K-lamprophyres. Their vaugneritic character is also evidenced by their positioning into the diagram of Fig. 2 where they plot clearly inside the vaugnerite field and, additionally, by the multi-elemental normalized diagram of Fig. 3, where the studied rocks present similar patterns to those reported for this type of rocks by Scarrow *et al.* (2009).

Fig. 2 – Discriminant function 1 – Discriminant function 2 plot; major elements, smaller dataset Sh: Shoshonite; Vg: Vaugnerite; K-La: K-lamprophyre (adapted from fig. 8; Scarrow *et al.*, 2009). half-circles: high-k dykes (this study).

Fig. 3 – Multi-element diagrams of the studied high-K rocks (half-circles) and of an average vaugnerite (line; values from Table 1; Scarrow *et al.*, 2009). PM: primitive mantle (Sun, 1980).

Genesis and geodynamic significance

In the absence of geochronological data and considering the poor outcropping conditions we must address the significance of the studied vaugnerite-like rocks with caution. The studied rocks are considered as dykes cutting the Devonian massifs of Vale de Maceira (c. 362 Ma; Moita *et al.*, 2005) and Veiros, yet no other time constraint exists.

The presence of Veiros' gabbro-monzonite association of shoshonitic affinity implies a source metasomatized by dehydration of a subduction slab beneath the area of study (see Lains, 2017; Ribeiro *et al.*, 1997). Furthermore, high-K rocks such as vaugnerites and potassic lamprophyres are also understood as a result of multi-stage process in which the involvement of a subduction-related metasomatic source is most likely (e.g. Von Raumer *et al.*, 2014; Scarrow *et al.*, 2011). Such model was proposed by Mata and Munhá (1986) for the calc-alkaline lamprophyres occurring in the vicinity of the studied area.

The studied vaugneritic rocks also present typical subduction-related characteristics such as high LILE and negative Nb-Ta anomaly and high K content (Fig. 3). However they are acid rocks and cannot be considered the result of partial melting of a mantle metasomatized source. This opens the possibility of their derivation by crystal fractionation from basic-intermediate shoshonitic melts similar to those at the origin of Veiros and Vale de Maceira massifs. Phlogopite, and minor brown amphibole, are significant hydrous phases in Veiros and Vale de Maceira massifs. Some of the chemical distinctive features of the vaugnerite dykes relative to Veiros, such as lower Nb/Ta; HREE; Rb and Cs and higher La/Yb ratios, may indeed result from biotite and hornblende fractionation, despite the role of crustal contamination cannot be dismissed.

In conclusion, high-K dykes of vaugneritic affinity and its probable genetic link with basic-intermediate calc-alkaline to shoshonitic rocks of Veiros and Vale de Maceira are considered a clear evidence for a dehydrating slab underneath the NE

domains of the OMZ during the Upper Palaeozoic.

This slab is here considered to be related to the northwards dipping subduction zone beneath the OMZ from Lower Devonian to Upper Devonian, as a result of the closure of the Palaeozoic Rheic Ocean. Magmatic evidence for the existence of such subduction with a northward polarity is given by the presence of the Lower to Middle Devonian tholeiite to calc-alkaline volcanic rocks of Mt. Covas Ruivas and Mt. Cortes at SW of the OMZ (see Santos *et al.*, 2013; 1990; Silva *et al.*, 2011) and Upper Devonian calc-alkaline to shoshonite intrusions of Veiros, Vale de Maceira (Lains, 2017, 2015) and Campo Maior (Carrilho Lopes *et al.*, 2005) at the northwest of OMZ.

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